

Visual identity, Press kit, Online Presence

D3.a

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5th October 2023

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Acronyms

EU	European Union
REA	European Research Executive Agency
STURM	SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing
RGB	Red, Green, and Blue
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, and Key
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

Overview

The deliverable D3.a - Visual identity, Press kit, Online Presence presents the visual identity, press kit, and online presence (social channels and website) of the SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing (STURM) project. It represents the initial results of T3.6 - Outreach and Communication activities, included in WP3 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation .

The communication strategy emphasizes transversal tools that can be adjusted and updated to keep pace with project advancements. These tools are designed for versatility, enabling online utilization to encourage extended participation. Moreover, their flexibility facilitates two-way interactions, fostering active citizen engagement. The visual identity serves as a cohesive representation of the project's essence, ensuring consistent recognition and reinforcing the strategy's effectiveness.

This document provides an overview of the visual identity concept and structure, including the STURM logo, colour palette, typography, and use guidelines. These elements serve as the blueprint for all communication materials and initiatives, including the project's press kit, social channels, and website. The website <https://sturm-weo.github.io/> was launched on 31st August 2023.

Visual Identity

The design process aimed to capture the project's key values of innovation, modernity, and trustworthiness.

The overall minimalist aesthetic evokes a sense of order, professionalism, and reliability while creating a contemporary and straightforward visual.

This visual language is further enhanced by the strategic use of clean lines, subdued colours, and balanced proportions.

All graphic elements are created using free and open-source tools, such as Inkscape,¹ embodying the commitment to Openness principles and practices throughout the project lifecycle.

1. Inkscape Website Developers, *About | Inkscape*, <https://inkscape.org/about/>, [Accessed 16-08-2023].

LOGO

The logo encapsulates the core ideals of the STURM project to resonate with the target audience. The design is simple and uncluttered, using basic geometric shapes like the square to symbolise the pixels of raster data and the circle encapsulating WEO's distinctive globe to symbolise Earth observations. The confident, clean lines depict the sub-pixel elements and simultaneously emphasise the reliability of the project's findings. The negative space suggests openness and transparency, reflecting the project's use of open-source data and a collaborative approach.

COLOUR LOGO - DARK VERSION

COLOUR LOGO - LIGHT VERSION

GRAYSCALE LOGO

MONOCHROME LOGO

Figure 1: Logo variations on different backgrounds

COLOUR PALETTE

Figure 2: Colour Palette

The colour palette (Figure 2) for STURM project's visual identity was crafted to convey the concepts of credibility and modernity according to the semantic space of colours.² In addition to this palette, the use of black and white is also possible. The main accent colour, a serene shade of blue, incorporates the water-related element while creating a seamless connection with the well-established brand identity of WEO (Figure 3).

Figure 3: WEO logo

Additionally, STURM palette gains depth and character with a selection of hues extracted from paintings by Claude-Joseph Vernet (Figure 4), reflective of the Sturm und Drang artistic movement, recalling the project name *STURM*, meaning *storm* in the German language.

2. Setsuko Horiguchi and Katsura Iwamatsu, 'From Munsell color system to a new color psychology system', *Color Research & Application* 43, no. 6 (October 2018): 827–839, <https://doi.org/10.1002/col.22286>.

Figure 4: "Der Sturm" (1752) by Claude-Joseph Vernet

TYPOGRAPHY

The typography (Figure 5) strengthens the project's visual identity based on a blend of elegance and authority, ensuring a consistent and captivating look across all STURM outputs.

The Poiret One font,³ chosen for the logo, headings, and titles, with its graceful and curvaceous letterforms, exudes a sense of creativity and modernity, echoing our innovative approach.

Complementing Poiret One font, Domitian font⁴ - or Palatino if not available, chosen for the body, lends a touch of timeless sophistication, emanating a sense of reliability and trustworthiness.

Both typefaces are available for different mediums, including \LaTeX , and are released with open licences that allow their use in products and projects –

3. *Poiret One* - Google Fonts — [fonts.google.com](https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Poiret+One/about), [https:// fonts.google.com / specimen / Poiret+One / about](https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Poiret+One/about), [Accessed 10-08-2023].

4. *GitHub* - [dbenjaminmiller/domitian: Domitian](https://github.com/dbenjaminmiller/domitian) — [github.com](https://github.com/dbenjaminmiller/domitian), [https:// github.com / dbenjaminmiller / domitian](https://github.com/dbenjaminmiller/domitian), [Accessed 10-08-2023].

be it print or digital, commercial or otherwise.

LOREM IPSUM

Lorem ipsum

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Figure 5: Typeface Combination

DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

To maintain consistency across the deliverables, a \LaTeX template has been created on Overleaf.

It is available at the following url: <https://tinyurl.com/sturmdev>.

The template is used in the present deliverable, exemplifying the commitment to maintaining uniformity and professional presentation standards throughout the project's documentation.

This template will also provide a framework for crafting presentation materials for conferences, workshops, online publications, and various dissemination events, to ensure widespread project recognition.

EUROPEAN FUNDING ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All STURM dissemination and communication materials should include the acknowledgement of EU support, along with displaying the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate), as shown in Figure 6.

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Figure 6: EU funding acknowledgement

Press kit

The press kit serves as a comprehensive resource for journalists, media outlets, and interested parties seeking accurate information about the project. To facilitate effective communication and outreach to broad audiences an official the press kit was translated into three European languages: English, French, and Italian.

The press kit includes the following key components:

- **Project Overview:** A concise summary of the STURM project, its objectives, and its significance.
- **Project Images:** High-resolution graphics related to the project, suitable for use in print and digital media.
- **Contact Information:** Details for inquiries, including website address and contact information.

ENGLISH VERSION

Project Overview

The SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing (STURM) project aims to advance urban flood research and mitigation by accurately mapping urban flood using open remote sensing imagery and in-situ crowdsourced data. The project addresses some key challenges in flood monitoring, including limitations related to spatial resolution and data accessibility. The specific objectives include mapping both flood extent and depth at urban scales with enhanced spatial resolution, exploiting global non-commercial resources and fusing data from various sources. The state-of-the-art deep learning-based pipeline ensures wide-ranging applicability by extracting the most from globally accessible data sources while minimizing the consumption of human and economic resources. The methodology will be validated through observations of real disaster events, thus also providing a benchmark for validating existing hydrological models. STURM is an EU-funded Research and Innovation project funded under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Postdoctoral Fellowships - European Fellowships (Grant agreement ID: 101105589) conducted by Nicla M. Notarangelo under the supervision of Charlotte Wirion and hosted at WEO.

Contact Informations

Website <https://sturm-weo.github.io/>

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Address WEO - Luxembourg-City Incubator, 9 rue du Laboratoire, L-1911 Luxembourg

FRENCH VERSION

Aperçu du Projet

Le projet SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing (STURM) vise à faire progresser la recherche et la mitigation des inondations urbaines en cartographiant avec précision les inondations urbaines à l'aide de données de télédétection "open source" et de données locales de "crowdsourcing". Le projet aborde certains défis clés liés à la surveillance des inondations, notamment les limitations liées à la résolution spatiale et à l'accessibilité des données. Les objectifs spécifiques comprennent la cartographie de l'extension et de la profondeur des inondations à l'échelle urbaine avec une résolution spatiale améliorée, en exploitant des ressources mondiales non commerciales et en fusionnant des données provenant de diverses sources. Le pipeline basé sur des techniques de pointe de l'apprentissage profond assure une applicabilité étendue en extrayant le meilleur des images de télédétection mondialement accessibles tout en minimisant la consommation de ressources humaines et économiques. La méthodologie sera validée avec des événements catastrophiques réels, fournissant ainsi une référence pour la validation des modèles hydrologiques existants. STURM est un projet de recherche et d'innovation financé par l'Union européenne dans le cadre des Actions Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSCA) Bourses postdoctorales - Bourses européennes (Numéro d'accord de subvention : 101105589), mené par Nicola M. Notarangelo sous la supervision de Charlotte Wirion et hébergé chez WEO.

Informations de Contact

Site Web <https://sturm-weo.github.io/>

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Adresse WEO - Luxembourg-City Incubator, 9 rue du Laboratoire, L-1911 Luxembourg

ITALIAN VERSION

Il Progetto

Il progetto SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing (STURM) mira a migliorare la ricerca e la mitigazione delle inondazioni in ambito urbano, attraverso una mappatura accurata delle caratteristiche fondamentali delle inondazioni urbane a partire da immagini satellitari *Open* e dati semantici e visivi *crowdsourced in situ*. Il progetto affronta alcune sfide chiave nel monitoraggio delle inondazioni, comprese le limitazioni legate alla risoluzione spaziale e all'accessibilità dei dati. Gli obiettivi specifici includono la mappatura dell'estensione e della profondità delle inondazioni in ambito urbano con una risoluzione spaziale migliorata, sfruttando risorse globali non commerciali e integrando dati provenienti da varie fonti. L'approccio basato su tecniche avanzate di *Deep Learning* garantisce un'ampia applicabilità sfruttando fonti di dati accessibili a livello globale, minimizzando al contempo il consumo di risorse umane ed economiche. La metodologia verrà convalidata attraverso osservazioni di eventi reali, fornendo così anche un punto di riferimento per la convalida dei modelli idrologici esistenti. STURM è un progetto di Ricerca e Innovazione finanziato dall'Unione Europea nell'ambito delle Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) - Postdoctoral Fellowships - European Fellowships (Accordo N.: 101105589), condotto da Nicola M. Notarangelo sotto la supervisione di Charlotte Wirion e ospitato presso WEO.

Informazioni di Contatto

Sito Web <https://sturm-weo.github.io/>

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Indirizzo WEO - Luxembourg-City Incubator, 9 rue du Laboratoire, L-1911 Lussemburgo

Online Presence

OFFICIAL WEBSITE

The STURM website serves as a portal for communication and dissemination activities, offering a comprehensive project overview accessible to both the scientific community and the general public.

In the pursuit of open science, the project's digital presence aligns with the principles of openness, transparency, and accessibility. To achieve this, the project website was strategically deployed on GitHub Pages. GitHub Pages provides a free and transparent hosting platform, allowing for the viewing of source code and project files. Furthermore, GitHub's version control system facilitates tracking changes made to the website over time.

The use of the Bootstrap CSS framework ensured that the design is responsive and adapts to different devices and screen sizes.

Moreover, the website facilitates broader engagement by enabling a RESOURCES section (providing tips, materials, and links for writing a successful MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship proposal and navigating project implementation) and an OUTCOMES section for all project outputs. Continuous updates will be made to the website, aligning it with the project's progress.

Figure 7: Website screenshot - landing page

Figure 8: Website screenshot - ABOUT section

Figure 9: Website screenshot - Project Timeline

RESOURCES

A continually revised collection of tips, materials, and links for writing a winning MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship proposal & navigating project implementation.

The 2023 call for MSCA-PF is open!

Who, what, and where, by what help, and by whose:

Why, how, and when, do many things disclose.

— Thomas Wilson, *The Arte of Rhetorique*.

The insights shared here emerge from my personal journey, and are continually enriched through conversations with other MSCA fellows and with those who aspire to become so. Keep those essential questions "What? Why? How? Where? When? Who? By what means?" in mind. Let these queries shape your decisions, whether you're picking a host institution or writing your proposals and reports. Stay curious and receptive to new ideas as an opportunity for growth and innovation. Cultivate appreciation and love for your research as the driving force when faced with challenges. Prioritise your well-being, emotional, and mental health as a solid foundation for success and satisfaction. Feel free to [get in touch](#) if you believe something should find a place here: every input is warmly welcome!

Figure 10: Website screenshot - RESOURCES section

Figure 11: Website screenshot - RESOURCES section

OUTCOMES

Stay tuned for updates on STURM progress and achievements. The main research outputs and deliverables, will be managed according to the FAIR principles.

Media
Coming soon

Data & Code
Coming soon

Publications
Coming soon

Figure 12: Website screenshot - OUTCOMES section

TEAM

Nicola M. Notarangelo
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow
Principal Investigator

Charlotte Wirion
Supervisor

WEO
Host Organization

Scroll Down

Figure 13: Website screenshot - TEAM section

Figure 14: Website screenshot - CONTACT section and acknowledgements

Since its public launch, the website reached more than 500 daily active users (Figure 15). This represents a significant preliminary achievement in the project, as the high number of daily active users suggests that the website is meeting the needs of its target audience. It is also a sign that the website is well-designed and easy to use.

Figure 15: Website insights - Daily active users

SOCIAL CHANNELS PRESENCE

The project also maintains an active presence on various social media platforms through the profiles of the team members and the host organization,

such as LinkedIn (Figure 16) and Twitter (Figure 17), as part of its strategic outreach efforts.

Figure 16: LinkedIn screenshot - More than 800 impressions

These platforms serve as channels for connecting with a wide-ranging audience and fostering connections within diverse communities. The social media strategy centres on delivering insightful academic and research-related content that engages the target audience.

Through these platforms, users are directed towards the project's dedicated website. An approach based on the use of relevant hashtags and effective content-sharing strategies is employed to enhance the project's visibility.

The tone is informative and engaging, and a regular posting will ensure a real-time narrative of the project's journey. Noteworthy and reliable content from other reputable sources will be cross-shared to stay updated with the latest developments, news, and events.

This approach not only enriches the audience's knowledge but also solidifies the project's reputation as a resource for valuable insights.

Figure 17: Twitter screenshot - More than 300 impressions

WHAT IS STURM? SmarT sub-pixel URban flood Mapping from open earth observation and crowdsourcing (STURM) project bolsters urban flood knowledge and resilience by providing enhanced flood extent and depth mapping.

Leveraging open Sentinel imagery, crowdsourcing, and state-of-the-art deep learning methods, STURM pioneers a globally applicable, smart, open-source-based approach to address spatial resolution and data gap challenges.

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